

Floating Gold: an International Collaboration through Estuary.

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ABSTRACT

Between December 2020 and November 2022 the Glasgow-based community group Gamelan Naga Mas worked remotely with two Indonesian musicians, Peni Candra Rini and Rangga Purnama Aji. This musical collaboration was made possible by the Estuary platform, which allowed for real-time livecoded improvisations between locations in Scotland, Indonesia, and the USA. In this paper we discuss and reflect upon the technical, musical, and human factors that have made this project a success and indicate some directions for future exploration.

1 Overview

Floating Gold (Naga Mas 2020a) is an international collaborative project by three creative artists: Peni Candra Rini, Rangga Purnama Aji (Indonesia) and Gamelan Naga Mas (Scotland and USA).

With the support of an International Collaboration Grant from the British Council, we have worked together over nearly two years to create eight audiovisual pieces that combine music improvised using the MiniTidal language in Estuary (Ogborn and Beverley 2017; Ogborn 2018) with vocal performances filmed in a range of Javanese locations.

The video series was launched on 21 November 2022 and is available online (Naga Mas 2022c) complete with Javanese subtitles and translations in English and Bahasa Indonesia.

The work was produced in two stages. In the first instance, improvised musical textures were created and recorded during collaborative livecoding sessions between Rangga Purnama Aji and four members of Naga Mas: Sen Sewell, Heather Strohschein, Bill Whitmer, and J Simon van der Walt. The music created was then sent to Indonesia where Peni Candra Rini worked with her team from Jagad Sentana Art to create the texts, vocal materials, and location videos. In this paper we concentrate primarily on the creation of the livecoded material.

2 Genesis

Gamelan Naga Mas is a community group based in Glasgow, Scotland with a stated purpose ‘... to play, study, compose and promote gamelan music and allied art forms of all kinds’. Since our formation in 1993 we have maintained a tradition both of performing traditional Indonesian music and of creating our own new work for and with the gamelan (Naga Mas 2022a).

In March 2020 the group found itself unable to play music together as a result of Covid-19 restrictions in the UK. We tried lending people instruments at home and playing together on Zoom, but, as many musicians discovered at that time, issues with latency (Ogborn 2018) and sound quality made that a less than rewarding experience.

One of our members, J Simon van der Walt, is active as a livecoder. In an attempt to keep the group going, Simon suggested that it might be possible for us to improvise something in the nature of gamelan music together using the MiniTidal language in the Estuary platform (Strohschein et al 2020).

Simon worked with the Network Imagination Laboratory (Network Imagination Laboratory 2022) to upload a set of samples created from recordings of the ‘Spirit of Hope’ gamelan instruments in Glasgow and created a set of video tutorials for the group based on Alex McLean’s ‘Learning Tidalcycles course’ (McLean 2020). Starting in April 2020 a practice developed of using the group’s regular Thursday evening rehearsal slot for a collaborative livecoding session.

Not everyone in the group chose to take part: from a regular attendance at live rehearsals of up to 15 players, the livecoding group dwindled to just seven. By July 2020 however, those taking part felt sufficiently confident to stream an improvised performance at the Network Music Festival (Naga Mas 2022b). This was followed in December 2020 by ‘The Waves Project’ (Naga Mas 2020b), a performance based around the composition *Waves* by group member Margaret Smith.

3 Collaboration

One of the chief affordances of Estuary is that, for each performer, all of the music is locally synchronised in time no matter the physical distance. Rather to our surprise, this allowed for one of our long-standing members who is based in Ohio USA, Heather Strohschein, to take part in our regular rehearsals, time zones permitting. Following this thought to its logical conclusion, the group decided to contact two Indonesian musicians with a view to a possible collaborative project.

The group had previously met Peni Candra Rini at the Festival of Gamelan and the Moving Image at the Royal Conservatoire of Scotland. The centrepiece of the festival was a performance of Garin Nugroho’s film *Setan Jawa* accompanied by live music composed by Rahayu Supanggah, that in turn prominently featured Peni’s highly distinctive work as a contemporary *sindhén*, the solo female voice in traditional Javanese music.

As well as being a virtuoso performer, Peni Candra Rini is one of the foremost composers and creative performers of contemporary gamelan music working in Indonesia today. As part of the festival, Gamelan Naga Mas were fortunate to be able to work together with Peni in a workshop setting. Since that time, it had been our joint hope that we would be able to collaborate again. Naga Mas approached Peni in March 2020, and she was happy to join the project, albeit as a composer, writer, and singer rather than as a coder.

Rangga Purnama Aji is a composer, electronic musician, songwriter, livecoder, video artist, self-taught generative and digital artist, and one of the initiators of Paguyuban Algorave Indonesia. Naga Mas were motivated to approach Rangga due to the explicit gamelan influence in his work, particularly evident in two album releases, *Little Kid Tripped Over A Star* (Rangga Purnama Aji 2019) and *KULA* (Rangga Purnama Aji 2020).

In turn, Rangga’s interest in the project arose from his realisation that this collaboration would be an opportunity to develop the growth of livecoding arts and to open the possible different approaches for Indonesian livecoding music. Other than that, the themes of the project are also related to Javanese traditional music and its vocal art. Rangga felt intrigued since gamelan and *macapat* became the thing that he wanted to explore more.

4 Inspirations

The name of the project ‘Floating Gold’ is an English translation of ‘Maskumambang’, the title of the first video we produced together. *Maskumambang*, in turn, is a Javanese poetic form that forms part of the *macapat* repertoire that can be sung either unaccompanied or with gamelan (Pickvance 2005:91; Pamuji et al 2020).

In early collaborative discussions, we went in search of cultural reference points that would make connections between Scotland and Indonesia. Naga Mas member Katherine Waumsley was inspired to draw out two metaphors from the phrase ‘floating gold’. The name of the group ‘Naga Mas’ translates as ‘golden dragons’ and led us to the image of our gamelan instruments ‘floating’ across the sea from Java to Scotland. The second resonance was explained to us by Peni: a Javanese image of ‘floating gold’ referring to the child floating in the womb.

Drawing these two threads together, Katherine wrote a text (Waumsley 2021) that wove these ideas together with a recounting of the Scottish myth of St Tenue (Campbell and Williamson 2009; Stevenson 2018), a pregnant woman who was cast out to sea by her family but then rescued by the fishes and brought to Glasgow, where she gave birth to the founder of the city, St Mungo. Themes of the sea, motherhood and the ancient Javanese *Majaphit* empire went on to inform both the Javanese texts created by Peni and, in some cases, the musical approaches taken in the coded improvisation.

4.1 Maskumambang

Tenue suci wanodya kinurmat nagri – Tenue a holy woman revered abroad

Glasgow ing mangsanya – Then in Glasgow

Abad nem putri britonic – Sixth century Brittonic princess

Nglairken putra minulya – Giving birth to a noble son

5 Collaborative Livecoding

Collaborative performance in real-time has been part of the livecoding scene since the very early days: in the recently published volume ‘Live coding a user’s manual’, Blackwell et al (2022) cite ensembles such as slub, Powerbooks_UnPlugged, Andrew Brown and Andrew Sorensen as aa_cell, Benoit and the Mandelbrots, and the Cybernetic Orchestra.

A number of platforms currently exist that are specifically designed to facilitate collaborative online performance, often in the browser, allowing for remote collaborations where participants do not need to be physically located in the same place. Alongside Estuary, the (probably incomplete) listing on the ‘Awesome Livecoding’ page (toplap 2022) notes several others, including kilobeat, Flok, Fragment, Troop, and Gibber.

To gauge the extent of the practice of remote collaborative coding, a brief survey was made into, as an example, the 104 performances given at a recent online streaming event, the ‘Longest Night Stream’ in December 2021 (toplap 2021). Of these, as far as can be ascertained from metadata and observing the recordings, just ten were remote collaborations, five using Estuary and five using Flok. One might speculate that in a context such as a free-for-all livestream, participants were more likely to want to show off their own individual musical and coding practices. The Floating Gold project, in contrast, is entirely dependent upon the existence of a simple browser-based collaborative platform: only two of our members, Simon and Rangga have an independent individual livecoding practice.

Two particular ensembles must be mentioned as having informed our work in Estuary: the Cybernetic Orchestra (McMaster 2022) and SuperContinent (Concordia 2021): the code-roulette strategy occasionally demonstrated by these ensembles was particularly productive for us in our early explorations.

6 How We Went About It

6.1 Gamelan Samples

The samples of the instruments used by the group in Estuary are mostly taken from the ‘Spirit of Hope’, an iron gamelan in the Yogyakarta style made by Suhirdjan circa 1990, that Naga Mas have stewardship of (Strohschein 2018).

Recordings of single notes from individual instruments were made at various times by different people and shared privately among members, often for the purposes of making demo recordings of gamelan compositions. Some of the sounds were also made available online, including on Freesound (van der Walt 2005) and as SoundFonts on the Internet Archive (van der Walt 2020).

A full Javanese gamelan comprises a complete set of instruments in two different tunings of seven and five notes respectively called *pelog* and *slendro* (Pickvance 2005). Historically Naga Mas have only had access to the *pelog* half of the gamelan and initial work was carried out using just that tuning. Partway through the project, the *slendro* half was also sampled to create a second set of sounds for Estuary. All of these sounds are now available on GitHub, together with a json ‘resource list’ (van der Walt 2021) that allows them to be loaded either permanently or on the fly into a collaborative ensemble in Estuary.¹

While it is probably impossible now to track the provenance of all of the samples exactly, we are confident that no commercial or other copyrighted samples were accidentally included, and we regard these now as CCO.

A hack was employed to map the samples in such a way that they would be easily usable by gamelan musicians: the banks of sounds for each of the tuned instruments have the lowest pitch sample duplicated. Gamelan musicians name *pelog* pitches using the numbers 1-7 from low to high. The lucky fact that samples are loaded into Estuary in name-sorted order means that, by putting an extra sample at 0, the following will play the correct pitches as a Javanese musician would name them:

```
n "6 5 3 2" # s "demung"
```

¹The reslist must be used in Estuary in order to load in the Naga Mas gamelan samples for the code examples listed below by entering this command:

```
!reslist https://github.com/tedthetrumpet/testpage/tree/master/nmsamples
```

6.2 Coding the Music

Between May 2021 and July 2022 the Floating Gold creative team would meet online in Zoom on Saturdays roughly fortnightly at around lunchtime in Scotland, corresponding to teatime in Indonesia and a rather early pre-breakfast slot in Ohio. After an individual check-in, we would discuss themes and ideas for the session, including possible musical and coding strategies.

After deciding what to work on, we would join a premade collaborative ensemble in Estuary. In earlier sessions we would leave Zoom running in the background as a backchannel for talking to each other while coding; as the project progressed and we became more secure in our approach to music and code, we found that less necessary, communicating when needed through the Estuary chat function.

As indicated above, Peni Candra Rini's role in the project was as a composer, writer, and singer rather than as a coder. During the coding sessions in Estuary, Peni would sometimes sing along in Zoom and sometimes just listen, with recordings of any sung improvisations through the Zoom platform made available for later review. These recordings were not used in the final project, being out of synchrony and of poor audio quality, but were useful as a vocal notepad for ideas.

A typical Estuary session would comprise three or four improvisations during the course of an hour, lasting anything from ten to thirty minutes. One of the team would screenshot and record both code and audio using OBS, with the resultant videos being shared privately between the group to listen back to.

In the weeks between the online meetings, sections of improvisation that seemed coherent and promising – the 'best bits' – would be trimmed out and saved as the basis for vocal work by Peni. The chosen sections ranged in length from roughly three to six minutes; although some of the improvisations sustained interest and energy over a longer period, our aim was for a series of individual song-length pieces rather than larger evolving structures.

In all but two cases, the final trimmed material represents a single continuous and uninterrupted stretch of improvisation. For the piece titled 'Pari', an eleven minute improvisation was reduced to six by judicious removal of over-repetitive material at cycle boundaries. In another case, a couple of cycles in MiniTidal were edited out where someone had accidentally put the gain up to 9 instead of 0.9, overwhelming the sound briefly.

6.3 Songs and Videos

For the second stage in the creation of each piece, individual audio files of the music were shared with Peni Candra Rini and her creative team in Indonesia. Working from these, Peni created a concept for each video including Javanese texts, costumes, movement, and locations, and, of course, the songs themselves.

For some of the videos, Peni sang live on location, working to a backing track playing on an earpiece: a particular challenge in the case of 'Welasana' where, at one point, Peni singing on a beach is almost engulfed by incoming waves! For other works, Peni worked with her team to record the vocal parts in a studio setting and then post-sync the vocal performance for the video.

The multi-camera shoots were variously compiled and edited by the team in Indonesia and/or a member of Naga Mas working in Scotland. The final production phase took place in Scotland, with the original code used to produce the music overlaid with the edited location videos and music tracks.

The poetry, the choreography and composition of the visuals deserve their own discussions but are outwith the scope of this paper.

7 Improvising 'Gamelan' Music Using Code

7.1 Coding Gamelan Music?

In our first flush of enthusiasm for working with Estuary, it seemed to us that the (purportedly) cyclical structures of Javanese gamelan that (allegedly) elaborate instrumental parts on the basis of a simple melody written in a numerical notation would be a perfect choice to express in formal terms in MiniTidal. And, there is indeed some low hanging fruit here. In a simplistic view of Javanese practice, the job of the *peking* instrument is to play twice each note that the *saron* instrument plays (Pickvance 2005:124). This is easily done:

```
slow 2 $ superimpose ((ply 2).(# s "peking")) $ n " 3 5 6 5 6 5 7 6"  
# s "saron"
```

In this particular example, taken from a well-known beginner's piece 'Lancaran Manyarsewu', a gong would play regularly at the end of each line:

```
slow 2 $ s "~!7 gong"
```

Already there are complications: as Javanese music is generally 'end-weighted', with the strong beat at the end of a group of notes rather than the start, it is necessary to take account of this in the code rather than going for the more obvious solution of `slow 2 $ s "gong"`.

Although it is possible to go on in this way and mock up complete MiniTidal versions of simple 'loud style' gamelan pieces, we found this after repeated attempts to be a largely pointless exercise. The results are unsubtle and mechanical, and do not capture any of the spontaneous interchange that would take place in a live performance of, say, 'Manyarsewu', where, for example, the drummer would be at liberty to cue a transition into one of a number of different variational forms.

Moreover, as Matthews (2018:98) explains, 'it would be an overgeneralization to describe the tradition as predominantly or explicitly rule-based'. The simplistic view of Javanese music as a cyclic skeletal melody elaborated by faster and slower moving voices – and therefore amenable to algorithmic analysis and resynthesis – is inadequate.

7.2 Coding 'Gamelan' Music

Rather than using MiniTidal to attempt an algorithmic recreation of traditional Javanese forms, we approached each improvisatory session in much the same way as a group of creative musicians might approach a physical gamelan: as if the ensemble we had in Estuary was our own shared 'virtual gamelan'. Furthermore, all of us are in some sense at least 'gamelan musicians', with an embodied sense of musical approaches, instrumental roles, and playing techniques, as well as an understanding of the culture and context of a range of Indonesian musics.

In some cases, this informed understanding of the affordances of the virtual ensemble led to straightforward solutions faced by each person in the group in deciding what to play. Again, if one imagines a group of gamelan musicians approaching a real gamelan, then there is a natural order of things where each individual will look to fill in where they are needed. Someone needs to take responsibility for the gong: a simple part, but with important structural implications. If there are already three *saron* players but no-one has yet sat down at the *peking*, someone would take on that job: and so on. Similarly, when we started an improvisation in Estuary, it was easy to look around at what other people were typing and see what was needed or, in some cases, again as one might do with a physical set of instruments, decide in advance that one person would take the drums, another the *kenong*, and so on.

7.3 Reflecting on the Code

Looking back at the improvised code used across the eight final videos that comprise the output to date of the Floating Gold project, there are some interesting approaches that emerge.

A feature of the first piece in the series, 'Maskumambang', is a sustained high note 5 in pelog (approximately A natural). This is intriguing, as sustained sounds are not that common to MiniTidal in Estuary. This instance was due to the combined effect of the vowel formant filter and a strong low pass filter resonance at the default frequency of 440Hz on a differently pitched (note 3) gong:

```
spin 4 $ (sometimes(jux(rev))) $ s "gong:3"  
# vowel "<a e i o u>"  
# up "-12" # resonance 0.99 # gain 0.5
```

It is also interesting to note that this track uses some non-gamelan sound banks, including 'kurt', 'peri', 'bd' and 'can' from the default bank. For the rest of the project, we limited ourselves to only using our own gamelan sounds.

In the improvisation that eventually became the underpinning for 'Ibu Bumi', we were seeking a way to make a verse/chorus structure. Looking at the code (Figure 1), we can see that the players on the left side are all working with code that begins `mask "<1 0>/8"` while those on the right hand side have `mask "<0 1>/8"` – in other words, eight cycles of music on the left side alternate with eight cycles on the right side.

A fundamental concept in Javanese music is *pathet* (Pickvance 2005:52), which, very approximately, corresponds to the idea of a mode: a flavour or colour of a piece that depends on the way in which the available pitches are ordered. Again,

Figure 1: Screenshot of 'Ibu Bumi' as improvised

as a vastly oversimplified example, a piece in the *slendro* tuning that featured the cadential phrase 3 2 1 6 and generally avoided the note 5 would indicate *pathet manyura*, while the same phrase one note lower 2 1 6 5 without a prominent 3 would be characteristic of *pathet sanga*.

This general line of thinking inspired another key feature of 'Ibu Bumi' that can be seen in the screenshot above (Figure 1): the players on the left side of the screen have an instruction to play only using the pitches 1, 2, 3 and 5, while those on the right side of the screen use only 2, 3 5 and 6. Taking into account the eight cycles on/off masking pattern, the result is a back and forth musical structure. This admittedly bears little resemblance to Javanese practice: it would be most unlikely for a traditional work to repeatedly change *pathet* on such a short timescale. However, regarding our aim to create relatively short song-like structures without resorting to preparation, the approach here was successful. In the final recording, one can clearly hear the piece begin with a syncopated pattern on the right hand side of the screen input by Heather:

```
mask "<0 1>/8" $ slow 2 $ n " 2 ~ 5 ~ 3 ~ 5 6 ~ 5 ~ 3 ~ 2 6 ~"
# s "sslenthem"
# up "[-12,12]"
```

This is followed after eight cycles by a melody created by Rangga on the left hand side using the alternate collection of notes:

```
mask "<1 0>/8" $ stack [
  s "sslenthem*2" # pan sine # n "1 5"
  , s "ssaron*4" # pan sine # n "2 3 1 <5 ~>"
]
```

As mentioned above, one of the thematic ideas of the Floating Gold project was thinking about the sea itself: the sea that, rather than drowning St Tenue, allowed her to be carried to safety with the help of the fishes.

In discussing the sea, we were struck by two meanings of the Indonesian/Javanese/Balinese word '*ombak*'. In its everyday sense it simply means 'wave' as in a wave in the ocean. In gamelan organology however, the word has a special meaning, referring to one of two kinds of timbral pulsation. In Balinese practice, pairs of instruments are purposely tuned a few cents apart (the lower known as *pengumbang*, the higher as *pengisep*) in order to create a shimmering tremolo effect from the beat frequencies (Paelinck and Vitale 2006). Similarly, Javanese gongs are purposely tuned in such a way that their pitch displays a low frequency pulsation (Pickvance 2005:203).

To manifest *ombak* in our coding, we hit upon the idea of using the speed controller to have the same sound being played simultaneously at slightly different pitches, just as in the Balinese gamelan. This technique was originated by Rangga and became something of a signature sound of his, copying and pasting lines within a stack and subtly changing the pitch of each. Here is a simple example of the technique as adopted by Heather in ‘Gayatri’:

```
!setbpm 50
stack [
  n "1 2 1 3" # s "ssaron",
  n "1 2 1 3" # s "ssaron" # speed 0.97
]
```

8 Future Work

All of the finished audiovisual works to date have been produced in two stages: musical material was generated through synchronous remote online improvisations as a first step, then the vocal parts and video were produced later. However, as noted above, during our development process Peni sometimes improvised along with us in Zoom while we coded in Estuary. Despite the substantial latencies and poor quality of the transmitted audio and video, this approach would seem to have promise. The main barrier to hybrid live-Estuary composition is bandwidth. While working solely within Estuary, there are no apparent disparities in internet bandwidth across sites, but when we include the transmission of bit-intensive audio or audiovisual live performance site-to-site, global disparities in bandwidth become readily apparent.

At the time of writing, Floating Gold are planning for a second phase of the project in the spring of 2023 that will explore more fully synchronous improvisation of the vocal parts. We will work with a series of open-form compositional frameworks that have been created by Rangga, that variously employ instructions, text prompts and graphical scores as a guide to improvisation for both the singer and the coders.

Two particular approaches to live performance have been discussed. In the first, Peni and Rangga would be physically located together for a public performance in Solo, Indonesia, with Naga Mas joining synchronously through a projected screen and audio amplification. This would at least provide fidelity in Solo at the performance and globally afterward. This approach, however, introduces scheduling issues; for the remainder of the project, Peni will be working abroad.

An alternative is to take advantage of the potentially better streaming fidelity – greater bandwidth, lower latency – where Peni is in residency. With this approach, we envisage a single performance that happens simultaneously for live audiences in more than one location, combining livecoding with live singing and even, perhaps, live gamelan playing. Both approaches highlight how bandwidth disparity can impact the aesthetic decisions of international collaborations.

9 Conclusions

The creative work we have achieved together so far as Floating Gold has exceeded our expectations. This is certainly the case of the video performances created by Peni and her artistic team. At the start of the project we envisaged something much more modest, perhaps a screengrab of an Estuary improvisation with a small inset video of Peni singing over Zoom. A full account of the creation of the texts, vocal parts, and location videos will have to wait for another paper, however.

One theory of ‘music’ is that we can think of it as an activity rather than a thing: not a noun, but a verb, ‘musicking’. (Small 1998; van der Walt 2011). As well as valuing the finished results, the project has been successful in enabling musicking, allowing us to create music together, despite being located on three different continents.

Reflecting on the process, a surprising and welcome outcome for us has been to affirm the strength and depth of, in its broadest sense, gamelan: to discover that the philosophies and practices that underpin Javanese music are strong enough to support and inform music made both live in a room with instruments and through a remote collaboration through the medium of livecoding.

9.1 Acknowledgments

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